

3-SHO‘BA SUN‘IY INTELLEKT

DETECTION OF GASTRIC ULCERS AND LESIONS APPLYING CNN ARCHITECTURE

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Annotation. Image recognition using artificial intelligence with deep learning through convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has dramatically improved and been increasingly applied to medical fields for diagnostic imaging. We developed a CNN that can automatically detect gastric ulcer and lesions in endoscopic images. The constructed CNN system for detecting gastric disease could process numerous stored endoscopic images in a very short time with clinically relevant diagnostic ability. It may be well applicable by reducing the load of endoscopists for daily clinical practice.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Networks, Endoscopy, Gastric Cancer, Gastric ulcers, lesions.

Introduction

Gastric cancer (GC) is one of the most common malignant tumors of the stomach mucosa. According to global statistics, GC is the second leading cause of cancer deaths, and the number of patients with GC is increasing due to changes in dietary habits and longer life expectancy [2]. GC may be effectively treated if detected early. Therefore, early detection and treatment of gastric cancer are essential. Radiography and endoscopy are used to screen for GC. During endoscopy, a specialist inserts an endoscope through the patient’s mouth or nose and directly observes the mucous membrane of the digestive tract to detect abnormalities. The detection sensitivity of GC by endoscopy is high, and if lesions are found during the examination, then tissue may be collected and simple treatment can be given [3]. Because gastroscopy can observe the gastrointestinal (GI) tract directly, it has been widely applied for GI examinations, which makes it more convenient for doctors to find lesions in the gastric mucosal surface. According to the evolution of cancerization, gastric lesions can be divided into three categories: advanced gastric cancer (AGC), early gastric cancer (EGC), and

gastric precancerous disease (GPD). Patients with AGC can rarely be cured, and the 5-year survival rate is no more than 30% [1]. Although the 5-year survival rate of EGC can achieve 90% [5], endoscopic diagnosis of EGC is indeed difficult in most countries [3], and largely depends on the doctors' experience and the device advancement. Statistics indicate that GPDs, like erosion, polyps, and ulcers, may transform into gastric cancer if they are misdiagnosed or are not treated in time [6].

Therefore, endoscopic detection of gastric cancer at an earlier stage is the single most effective measure for reducing gastric cancer mortality. It also offers an opportunity to treat patients with organ-preserving endoscopic therapy such as endoscopic mucosal resection or endoscopic sub mucosal dissection (ESD) [6–12]. Although esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) is the standard procedure for diagnosing gastric cancer, the false-negative rate for detecting gastric cancer with EGD is 4.6–25.8% [7]. Furthermore, inexperienced endoscopists tend to overlook gastric cancer because most cases arise from atrophic mucosa. In addition, some early gastric cancer lesions show only subtle morphologic changes, which are difficult to distinguish from background mucosa with atrophic change. Therefore, endoscopists require long-term specific training and experience to detect gastric cancer properly. In recent years, image recognition using artificial intelligence (AI) with machine learning has dramatically improved and been increasingly applied to diagnostic imaging in various medical fields.

Methods.

Convolutional Neural Networks. Deep learning, which represents a new method of machine learning, enables machines to analyze various training images and extract specific clinical features using a backpropagation algorithm [8]. Based on the accumulated clinical features, machines can diagnose newly acquired clinical images prospectively. This type of deep learning system has become possible through the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that logically imitate the structure and activity of brain neurons on a computer. Various kinds of neural networks have been developed, and CNN is particularly known as the best performance model in the field of image recognition [8]. Fitting optimal parameter values automatically is called learning of the neural network, and properly defining these parameters determines the neural network's ability. Supervised learning uses data sets consisting of both input and appropriate output information. Thus, deep learning through a CNN [9-10] using extensive image data has a high potential for clinical application in recognizing clinical images. To develop deep learning through a CNN to detect early and advanced gastric cancer, we constructed an AI-based diagnostic system that was trained by more than 13,000 images of EGD. We then tested the diagnostic accuracy of this

system to detect gastric cancer

A CNN used for segmentation rather than object detection analyzes patterns in the local regions of the image and divides the entire image into regions by determining whether they match the patterns to be extracted. This behavior involved in determining individual regions while observing details is similar to that used by an expert physician when observing the gastric cavity, and segmentation techniques may be able to improve the accuracy of automated lesion detection. On the other hand, many small regions are often observed in the segmentation output by CNNs. Excluding these using the FP reduction technique may greatly reduce the number of FPs and improve detection performance. Therefore, segmentation techniques that exclude small excess regions are effective for the automated detection of GC and identification of the extent of invasion.

In this work proposed a new integrated CNN called the Gastric Ulcer&Lesion detector network; this is a concise network and can recognize ulcers and lesion in GI tract. Our GULDNet support endoscopic doctors decrease misdiagnosis and screen out images containing lesions to alleviate doctors' workloads. At the beginning endoscopic image is preprocessed to eliminate noises such as blur, defocus, bubbles, and glare. Then preprocessed image is gathered as dataset to train model. Model can be retrained iteratively to improve detection level of ulcers and lesion GI tract.

Preparation of training and test image sets

The main criteria to endoscopic images were images with standard white light, chromoendoscopy using indigo carmine spraying, and narrow band imaging (NBI). The secondary criteria were any images that were magnified as well as poor quality images resulting from less insufflation of air, post-biopsy bleeding, blur, defocus, or mucus. After selection, 10,000 images were collected for 2600 histologically proven gastric cancer lesions as a training image data set. At least one gastric cancer lesion was presented in all images, and multiple images were prepared for a same lesion to include differences in angle, distance, and extension of the gastric wall.

Figure 2. a) Lesion area and ulcers are defined by an expert b) real image c) detected ulcers by program

An expert on gastric cancer marked all images of gastric cancer lesions manually. The expert carefully marked the range of cancer lesions using rectangular frames (Fig. 1). To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of the constructed CNN, an independent test data set of stomach images was collected from 69 consecutive patients with 77 gastric cancer lesions, who received an EGD during daily clinical practice. All EGD procedures used a standard endoscope and a standard endoscopic video system. During the procedure, an entire stomach was observed, and images of all parts were captured with white light images. The chromoendoscopy, NBI, and poor-quality images were excluded.

Conclusion. In this paper, we established a CNN called GULDNet to classify two categories of gastric diseases using stored endoscopic images, which processed extensive independent images in a very short time. The clinically relevant diagnostic ability of the CNN offers a promising applicability to daily clinical practice for reducing the burden of endoscopists as well as telemedicine in remote and rural areas as well as in developing countries where the number of endoscopists is limited.

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